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Factors influencing the digital competence of students in basic vocational education training

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Abstract

Digital competence (DC) is essential in order for individuals to actively participate in all sectors of society. While high school students' DC has been studied extensively, few studies have examined DC in vocational education and training (VET). To address this gap, a study in the context of the Basque Autonomous Community was carried out with the objectives of measuring Basic VET students' DC perceptions and investigating the factors that have an impact on Basic VET students' DC. Descriptive and multilevel analyses were conducted. The results indicate a need to focus on enhancing Basic VET students' DC, as these skills are critical for their professional development. Furthermore, school predictors were found to be the strongest predictors of students' DC, followed by attitude toward information and communication technologies and the frequency of technology use for school-related and personal purposes. This study provides knowledge that could help educational institutions identify areas for further improvement in fostering students' DC, and provides policy makers with a comprehensive understanding of the present situation of VET students' DC.

Keywords Students' digital competence, Vocational education and training, School digital capacity, Digital transformation

Introduction

Digitalisation has had a great impact on society and this is why the 21st century is known as the technology era (Zhao *et al.* 2021). The labour market has been changed by digitalisation and the advancements of Industry 4.0, requiring education systems to adapt their offerings to align with its evolving demands (Wild and Schulze Heuling 2020). Thus, new skills and competences are needed due to the growing importance of technology (Findeisen and Wild 2022). Digital competence (DC) is one of the key competences for lifelong learning (European Commission 2019) since it enables individuals to play an active role in all areas of society (González-Martínez *et al.* 2018). Notwithstanding the assumption that young people possess sufficient digital skills, studies reveal that they do not necessarily possess the appropriate digital knowledge often attributed

to them (Kirschner and De Bruyckere 2017). In several studies it has been concluded that young people do not possess an optimal level of DC, despite having grown up in a digital technology context (Estanyol et al. 2023; Gallardo Echenique et al. 2015; Kennedy et al. 2009; Valverde-Crespo et al. 2020).

Education is essential for the progress of society (Kovalchuk et al. 2023) and vocational education and training (VET) plays a crucial role in meeting the needs of the labour market and society (Cattaneo et al. 2022). In order to significantly impact businesses and individuals, VET should prepare young people (Basque Government 2022a; Cedefop 2023a), providing environments in which students develop their digital skills (Subrahmanyam 2022). Digital transformation has become a priority in Europe (European Education and Culture Executive Agency 2019) and the need to work on DC has been integrated into educational policy in VET (Cedefop 2023a). Basic VET is one of the Basque Autonomous Community (BAC), designed to reduce early school leaving (Basque Government 2015, 2016; Cedefop 2023b). Nevertheless, basic VET students' DC has rarely been studied (Aguilar de la Rosa, 2022). Given that the development of Industry 4.0 is reshaping work structures and making DC a core requirement across all sectors (Indrawan and Lay 2019; Cedefop 2023a), further research on this group is highly relevant.

Thus, the present study analyses Basic VET students' perceptions of DC in the Basque Autonomous Community (BAC) as well as the personal and contextual factors that influence those perceptions. It offers insights that can provide educational institutions with knowledge that will allow them to identify areas for enhancing students' DC and equips policymakers with a thorough understanding of VET students' digital landscape. To achieve this, first, the theoretical framework is presented to contextualise the study. The subsequent section details the methodological approach adopted. The results are then reported and further examined in the discussion. Finally, the conclusions highlight the main contributions, implications, and avenues for future research.

Theoretical framework

Digital competence

DC is a key competence for lifelong learning, defined as “confident, critical and responsible use of, and engagement with, digital technologies for learning, at work, and for participation in society” (European Commission 2019, p. 10). According to Larraz (2013), it involves the ability to mobilise information, technological, multimedia, and communication literacies to process information, share knowledge, and solve problems. Information literacy involves the capacity to articulate it, locate it, evaluate it, organise it, transform it into knowledge and communicate it appropriately in a given context. Technological literacy refers to the ability to process data in several formats, adequately and effectively adapting it to the public and the context. This implies a technical mastery of the organisation and management of technical devices. Multimedia literacy entails analysing and creating multimodal digital messages from a critical perspective. Finally, communication literacy enables safe, ethical, and responsible interaction and collaboration in digital environments, forming the basis of digital citizenship.

Hence, the integration of these four literacies facilitates individuals to make informed decisions across all areas of the learning ecosystem, whether personal, professional, or social. Given this interrelated nature of DC, an instrument called INCOTIC 2.0 was

developed as its assessment requires an instrument capable of capturing its constituent literacies (González-Martínez et al. 2018).

Research using the INCOTIC 2.0 instrument at the university level reveals key patterns in students' self-perceived DC across its four core literacies. Findings show a common trend of high multimedia literacy but low technological literacy (Llopis Nebot et al. 2018; Sánchez-Caballé et al. 2019). However, other studies report high information and low communication literacy instead, with the indicator related to publication under the Creative Commons license yielding the lowest score (Henríquez Coronel et al. 2018). These differences likely reflect varying academic contexts and disciplinary demands. Additionally, the use of digital technologies for leisure had the highest scores (Henríquez Coronel et al. 2018; Sánchez-Caballé et al. 2019), higher than the scores for the use of these technologies for school-related purposes; this is consistent with the results of previous studies (Gisbert Cervera et al. 2016; Larraz 2013). Furthermore, the results showed that students have a highly positive attitude toward technology (Sánchez-Caballé et al. 2019), also in line with previous analyses (Kivunja 2015; Prendes et al. 2010).

To the best of our knowledge, no prior studies have employed the INCOTIC 2.0 instrument to investigate DC at non-university educational levels. Its theoretical robustness, derived from a close alignment with Larraz's (2013) multidimensional definition of DC, provides a solid foundation for this application. Given that these dimensions of DC are transferable across educational contexts, the questionnaire is suitable for the VET context, where the curriculum is explicitly designed to bridge the gap between education and labour market demands (Wild and Schulze Heuling 2020). Therefore, the INCOTIC 2.0 provides a robust framework to assess VET students' digital readiness for labour market demands, as its four core literacies are crucial for developing the holistic skill set needed to navigate complex challenges and make informed decisions in all areas of life. To this end, the present study analyses VET students' perceptions of DC and the factors that impact it.

Students' DC in VET

The progress of society relies on how education develops and VET is one of the most important pillars that lead to successful economic development (Kovalchuk et al. 2023). It prepares future qualified workers who are aligned with the needs and requirements of the labour market by promoting training in order to achieve a high level of professional competency (Kovalchuk et al. 2023). The rapid development of Industry 4.0 is reshaping work structures, presenting significant challenges for adaptation (Indrawan and Lay 2019); in response, DC is becoming fundamental for nearly all occupations (Cedefop 2023a). Despite the fact that 90% of jobs in all sectors require some form of digital skills and that these required skills will shift from basic to advanced in the future, 35% of European workers still lack these skills (European Commission 2020). To address this situation, Europe has established a goal for a minimum of 80% of the population to possess basic digital skills by 2030 (European Commission 2022a). Therefore, the development of students' DC is an important aspect of their training (Kovalchuk et al. 2023).

This is why Basic VET students must be digitally competent and fully able to make appropriate use of digital technologies (Moreno Guerrero et al. 2019). However, each student has their own specific digital characteristics depending on their prior educational experience (Moreno Guerrero et al. 2019). According to Aguilar de la Rosa (2022),

VET students' DC and digital technology use have not been frequently studied, and the few studies in his review demonstrate that VET students show lower DC perception levels than students in other stages of higher education. In another study on German VET, it was found that students do not have problems navigating the Internet but do experience difficulties when searching for information and reading Web content (Burchert et al. 2013). The DC of students in cooperative higher education and VET was compared in a study (Wild and Schulze Heuling 2020), which found that the DC level of cooperative higher education students was more advanced than that of VET students. Furthermore, several studies indicate that there is a higher affinity for using digital technologies for private purposes rather than for professional or educational reasons (Aguilar de la Rosa, 2022; Burchert et al. 2013).

Regarding the frequency of technology use, the literature shows that VET students lack DC from a pedagogical perspective, although they possess these competences from a technological perspective (Moreno Guerrero et al. 2019). However, Moreno Guerrero's analysis is based primarily on the use of digital technology for different purposes rather than on analysing the ability to manage the four literacies, which better aligns with the definition of DC (Larraz 2013) adopted here. Thus, the present study focuses on analysing Basic VET students' DC based on the four literacies rather than merely studying the frequency of use of digital technologies.

Factors influencing DC

DC encompasses a range of factors, at both the contextual and personal levels, that are essential for effectively navigating the digital landscape. These factors have been extensively studied in the context of educators, with significant research focusing on teachers (Cattaneo et al. 2022; Lucas et al. 2021). However, when examining students, the situation is notably different.

The school context plays a crucial role in shaping students' DC. Nevertheless, there is a noticeable gap in research examining exactly how this context influences the development of students' DC. Education should help learners to develop their DC (European Commission 2020). Therefore, in terms of skills development, research and knowledge generation, the educational system must adapt to the needs of the digital revolution (Basque Government 2022b). Considering this transformation scenario, DC must be established as a fundamental element in order to guarantee opportunities for digital technologies in teaching and learning environments (Basque Government 2022b).

For a successful digital transformation in education, schools' digital capacity must be increased in order to support the effective integration of technology (Costa et al. 2021). Digital capacity is defined as the effective integration of technology into teaching and learning processes through the school's cultural environment, policies, infrastructure and students' and teachers' DC (Costa et al. 2021). With the objective of helping schools to determine their degree of digital capacity, the SELFIE tool was designed (European Commission 2022b). The tool provides schools with a holistic view of organisational strategies for the school's digital transformation, taking 8 areas into account (European Commission 2022b): Leadership, Collaboration and networking, Infrastructure and equipment, Continuing professional development, Pedagogy – support and resources, Pedagogy – implementation in the classroom, Assessment practices, and Student digital competence.

Beyond contextual influences, it is crucial to consider the personal factors influencing DC (González-Martínez et al. 2018), as they provide critical insights into the individual differences that explain why students with similar access to technology and training often exhibit varying levels of proficiency. Several factors have been analysed at different educational levels, including gender, previous educational experience, the frequency of use of digital technologies, attitudes toward ICTs, age, and educational and professional qualifications.

In terms of gender, while some studies carried out in secondary education have demonstrated that males have a greater perception of DC (Fuster-Rico et al. 2025; Niño-Cortés et al. 2023), others conclude that females have a better perception of this competence (Fraillon et al. 2014). Another study at the same educational level found statistically significant gender differences only in communicative literacy, with boys perceiving themselves as more proficient than girls (Verdú-Pina et al. 2024). Regarding students' previous educational experiences, a study with lower-secondary students concluded that prior academic achievement is one of the most important predictors of students' DC (Hatlevik et al. 2015). Additionally, in studies on the use of digital technologies in higher education, it was concluded that students' DC perception was related to their frequency of use of ICTs (Esteve Mon 2015; González-Martínez et al. 2018) as well as to their attitudes toward ICTs (Browne 2009; Edmunds et al. 2012; González-Martínez et al. 2018; Sang et al. 2010). On the other hand, some studies in higher education revealed that students' attitudes toward the use of ICTs are positive when they are useful to reach the objective and easy to use (Edmunds et al. 2012; Espuny Vidal et al. 2011).

Findeisen and Wild (2022) analysed factors influencing commercial VET students' DC perceptions, highlighting the positive impact of professional qualifications, the frequency of use in some learning opportunities (the use of devices to search for content/information on the Internet, the use of office programs, reading blogs or forums, and creating blog entries) and the frequency of use of instant messaging services. Conversely, online learning had a negative impact, suggesting it is not seen as relevant to DC development. However, the research was based on the commercial VET sector, and the conclusions cannot be extended to other VET fields. Thus, in the present research, additional factors that have an impact on Basic VET students' DC will be analysed.

To date, few studies have considered both personal and contextual factors when analysing students' DC. Zhong (2011) found that the ICT penetration rate negatively impacts students' digital skill perception, indicating that the presence of ICTs does not guarantee greater opportunities to use ICTs or to work on literacy. The history of using ICTs and ICT use at home and at school showed a positive impact on their digital skill perception, with their use of ICTs at home as the greatest predictor. Nevertheless, this previous study does not analyse the pedagogical use of ICTs or school digital implementation based on the factors that have an impact on students' digital skills.

Hippe and Jakubowski (2022) used SELFIE data to analyse differences in students' DC across countries, schools, and individuals. The results revealed that at the student level, individual perceptions of infrastructure, pedagogy, and assessments were strongly related to their DC. At the school level, the aggregation of these student perceptions (school climate) showed an even stronger association with DC. In contrast, teacher-reported indicators were not significant in explaining variations. At the country level, differences in DC were linked to perceived support for teacher pedagogy and access to

digital resources. Nevertheless, students' DC was based on SELFIE results, and the focus was on measuring the impact of several predictors on the opportunities that students have to work on their DC in schools. To the best of our knowledge, no studies have yet investigated VET students' DC in relation to personal and school (digital capacity) factors. Therefore, the present study also aims to identify the factors that have the strongest impact on students' DC perception.

The specific context of the study

Against the international background provided so far, the Spanish VET system aims to train professionals for specific occupations and direct labour market entry (Aguilar de la Rosa, 2022). Basic VET is one of the VET levels offered in the BAC (Basque Government 2016) as it is in Spain. The aim of Basic VET is to promote student retention in the education system by offering other opportunities to obtain a Compulsory Secondary Education Graduation Certificate as well as a basic technician diploma (Basque Government 2015; Cedefop 2023b). Through Basic VET, students not only acquire professional qualifications but also develop essential skills (Moreno Guerrero et al. 2019), such as digital skills (Basque Government 2022a). As the demand for digital skills in the labour market is increasing, the need to work on DC has been integrated into VET educational policy (Cedefop 2023a). The Spanish VET modernisation plan includes a strategy to promote digitalisation for economic and social growth (Spanish Government 2020). Aligned with this, the 6th Basque VET plan aims to expand digital transformation and encourage the pedagogical use of digital technologies (Basque Government 2022a).

Aims and research questions

As indicated by the discussion above, no studies could be found on Basic VET students' DC perceptions, as previous analyses were carried out with students at other educational levels (Henríquez Coronel et al. 2018; Llopis Nebot et al. 2018; Sánchez-Caballé et al. 2019). Additionally, the available research on the use of digital devices for other purposes (Moreno Guerrero et al. 2019) was based on a specific VET field and country (Findeisen and Wild 2022). Finally, we found no studies that consider the interactions among personal and school factors as they relate to students' DC perceptions. Thus, the present study aims to measure Basic VET students' perceived DC in the BAC, identify the effects of personal and school factors on it, and determine the strongest predictors of their DC. To do so, the following research questions were posed:

RQ1: What are the attitudes toward ICTs, frequency of use of digital technologies and DC perceptions of Basic VET students in the BAC?

RQ2: How do the school's degree of digital capacity, the SELFIE areas, and the students' personal characteristics influence Basic VET students' DC perceptions?

Method

Sample

The data employed in this study were obtained from BAC Basic VET schools. The sample consisted of 857 students from 21 schools, and data collection was carried out during April and May of 2023. The distribution of students across the VET work areas in the study was as follows: 28.4% in industry and manufacturing, 25.7% in sport and well-being, 13.2% in hospitality, tourism and commerce, 11.9% in technology and innovation,

9% in transport and automotive, 3.9% in administration and management, 3% in hospitality, tourism and commerce, 2.8% in agriculture, fisheries and the rural environment, and 2.1% in arts, design and communication. The gender distribution of the participants was as follows: 32.7% female, 59.6% male, 3.4% non-binary, and 4.3% preferred not to answer (Appendix A). Schools were assigned numbers in place of names to maintain anonymity.

Instruments

INCOTIC: measuring students' DC perception

McDonald's omega analysis was conducted in order to determine the reliability of the INCOTIC 2.0 instrument (González-Martínez et al. 2018) with Basic VET students. The results indicate that the instrument can be considered reliable, with all subscales having a McDonald's omega value ranging from 0.807 to 0.855 (Table 1). The questionnaire consisted of five sections: demographic information, technological profile, DC perception, attitude toward ICTs, and technoethics.

The students' demographic information, such as gender, type of studies and school, were collected in the first section of the questionnaire. All other items were answered on a 5-point Likert scale. Four items gathered the students' technological profile responses on a scale from 1 ("I completely disagree") to 5 ("I strongly agree"). Two of these items were related to the students' frequency of use of digital technologies for leisure or school-related purposes (e.g., "I am a person who uses digital tools a lot in my personal life") and two were related to their need for telephone and Internet services (e.g., "I couldn't live without my mobile phone"). A total of 19 items measured the subjects' DC perceptions, with responses on a scale from 1 ("I do not know how to do this") to 5 ("I can do this without difficulty"); these were divided into four dimensions: Information (e.g., "Saving all links to classwork information in an orderly manner"), Technology (e.g., "Connect to the most secure Wi-Fi network available"), Multimedia (e.g., "Realize when I'm being tricked by a multimedia message") and Communication (e.g., "Work collaboratively on a shared document in the cloud"). Nine items gathered information on the students' attitudes toward ICTs (e.g., "They help me learn autonomously") and five items measured their technoethics (e.g., "I'm concerned about my security and privacy on the Internet") on a scale from 1 ("I completely disagree") to 5 ("I strongly agree").

Table 1 General indicators of INCOTIC 2.0

Scale reliability statistics	
	McDonald's
Scale	0.846
Item Reliability Statistics	
Technological profile	0.855
Digital competence	
1. Information literacy	0.807
2. Technological literacy	0.807
3. Multimedia literacy	0.810
4. Communication literacy	0.822
Attitude toward ICTs	0.818
Technoethics	0.835

SELFIE: measuring the digital capacity of schools

McDonald's omega analysis was conducted (Table 2) in order to determine the reliability of the SELFIE tool (European Commission 2022b). The results indicate that the instrument can be considered reliable, with all subscales having a McDonald's omega value ranging from 0.942 to 0.952 (Table 2). All items employed a 5-point Likert scale, with responses ranging from 1 ("I completely disagree/I do not do this at all") to 5 ("Strongly agree/I do this very well"), including an option for "Not Applicable" (N/A).

The survey was completed by each school's management team members, teachers and students in order to gather information on their experience of digital implementation in their schools (European Commission 2022b). Management team members and teachers completed a 31-item questionnaire encompassing Leadership (e.g., "At our school, we have a digital strategy"), Collaboration and networking (e.g., "At our school, we use digital technologies when collaborating with other institutions"), Infrastructure and equipment (e.g., "At our center, there are digital devices for teaching use"), Continuing professional development (e.g., "Our management team discusses digital technologies with us in relation to continuing professional training needs related to education"), Pedagogy in terms of support and resources (e.g., "Our teachers seek online educational resources"), Pedagogy related to classroom implementation (e.g., "I use digital technologies in my teaching method to adapt to the needs of each student"), Assessment practices (e.g., "Our teachers use digital technologies to assess students' abilities"), and Student digital competence (e.g., "At our school, students learn how to act safely on the Internet"). Students, on the other hand, completed an 18-item questionnaire focusing on Infrastructure and equipment (e.g., "At our school, I have access to the Internet to learn"), Pedagogy related to classroom implementation (e.g., "At our school, when I use technology, I participate more"), and Student digital competence (e.g., "At our school, I learn how to determine whether the information I find on the Internet is reliable and correct"). This tailored approach ensured that the information collected reflected the school's digital capacity, incorporating the direct participation of each group involved in the implementation of digitalisation.

Data collection

Data were collected through online surveys. For the SELFIE questionnaire, direct links were provided by the SELFIE coordinator of each school to management team members, teachers and students, and each profile had its own link. Once the surveys were completed, SELFIE reports were requested from all schools. Regarding INCOTIC 2.0, a

Table 2 General indicators of SELFIE

Scale reliability statistics	
	<i>McDonald's</i>
Scale	0.952
Item Reliability Statistics	
Leadership	0.949
Collaboration and networking	0.945
Infrastructure and equipment	0.948
Continuing professional development	0.951
Pedagogy: support and resources	0.945
Pedagogy: implementation in the classroom	0.943
Assessment practices	0.943
Student digital competence	0.942

direct link was provided to students. For both surveys, informed consent was obtained from all participants, and confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout the research process. This study was conducted always considering the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the American Psychological Association.

Analysis

All analyses in this study were conducted using R (version 4.4.0). First, descriptive statistics were generated to explain the means and standard deviations for the scores of students' attitudes toward ICTs, frequency of use of digital technologies for personal and school-related purposes, and DC perceptions.

Additionally, considering that students (first level) are nested within schools (second level), multilevel linear modelings (MLMs) were conducted to answer RQ2. In the MLM analysis, all schools with at least 10 student participants were included, as this was deemed an appropriate number following Schmitz et al.'s (2022) study. In order to determine whether an MLM analysis was necessary, an unconditional model (null model) was estimated to test whether differences in students' DC perceptions could be found at the individual and school levels. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to compare a single-level model. Furthermore, the intraclass correlation (ICC) for students' DC perceptions was computed in order to determine what proportion of the total variance in those perceptions is attributable to differences among schools.

Next, grand mean centering was applied to center the predictors, which made it possible to determine the average effect of student and school characteristics. After that, random intercept MLM analyses were conducted. Two different models were created to answer RQ2. However, in order to confirm that these two models were the appropriate ones, different models were compared (including and excluding different predictors) using ANOVA and considering the Akaike information criterion (AIC), the Bayesian information criterion (BIC) and log-likelihood (logLik). For the first model, the level 1 predictors were attitudes toward ICTs and the use of digital technologies for personal and school-related purposes, and the level 2 predictor was the school's degree of digital capacity, considering the mean of all SELFIE areas. In order to determine which SELFIE areas were significant predictors of the students' DC perceptions, a breakdown of the areas was made. For the second model, the level 1 predictors were the same as those for the first model but, after comparing different models (Appendix B), only three SELFIE areas were considered appropriate level 2 predictors: Pedagogy (support and resources), Pedagogy (implementation in the classroom) and Assessment practices. These areas are related to the integration of digital technologies in teaching and learning processes, thus it is expected that they would have a direct impact on students. Finally, 95% confidence intervals were calculated to determine the precision of the results.

Results

Descriptive analyses

To address RQ1, descriptive statistics—including means and standard deviations—were calculated to analyse the means and standard deviations of students' frequency of use of digital technologies for personal and school-related purposes and DC perception. With respect to the frequency of use of digital technology, higher scores were obtained for personal use ($M = 3.86$; $SD = 1.24$) than for school-related use ($M = 2.89$; $SD = 1.32$).

Regarding DC perception (Fig. 1), the lowest scores were obtained for communicative aspects ($M = 3.09$; $SD = 0.92$), with the item related to publishing digital content under a Creative Commons license showing the lowest mean score across the entire scale ($M = 2.29$; $SD = 1.33$). In contrast, the highest scores were related to multimedia aspects ($M = 3.53$; $SD = 0.90$).

MLM analyses

To answer RQ2, ANOVA results showed a significant improvement in fit when including the random intercept. According to students' DC perceptions, there were reductions in AIC (from 1962.242 to 1901.284) and BIC (from 1971.749 to 1915.544). Furthermore, the ICC analysis of the null model indicated that 12.5% of the variance could be attributed to differences in schools. This variability is considered meaningful, as it suggests that students' perceptions are not solely shaped by individual characteristics but are also influenced by the school context. Therefore, it was concluded that there were significant differences reflected in school variability scores in the students' DC perceptions.

The MLM results showed that in Model 1, all predictors had a significant positive impact, with the strongest impact being the school's degree of digital capacity ($\beta = 0.26$). While Model 1 considered the school's overall digital capacity as a general predictor, Model 2 provides a more detailed view by breaking this construct into specific dimensions, allowing us to identify which aspects of school digital capacity exert the strongest influence on students' DC perceptions. The Model 2 results indicate that all predictors had a significant positive impact except Pedagogy: implementation in the classroom, which had a significant negative impact. The strongest impacts were found for Pedagogy: support and resources ($\beta = 0.27$), followed by Assessment practices ($\beta = 0.26$), Pedagogy: implementation in the classroom ($\beta = -0.26$), Attitude toward ICTs ($\beta = 0.24$), and Use of digital technologies for school-related ($\beta = 0.19$) and personal ($\beta = 0.08$) purposes. The R^2_m value indicates that 23.3% of the variability in students' DC perceptions can be explained by fixed effects and R^2_c represents 25.5% of the total variability. The difference between R^2_m and R^2_c is 2.2%. The results are presented in Table 3.

Fig. 1 Descriptive analyses of DC perceptions

Table 3 Results of the MLM

	Null model	Model 1		Model 2	
		β	95% CI (Model 1)	β	95% CI (Model 1)
Fixed					
Intercept	3.26 (0.06)***	1.93 (0.11)***	[1.71, 2.15]	1.93 (0.11)***	[1.71, 2.14]
Use of digital technologies for school-related purposes		0.10 (0.01)***	0.18 [0.07, 0.14]	0.11 (0.01)***	0.19 [0.07, 0.14]
Attitude toward ICTs		0.24 (0.03)***	0.24 [0.17, 0.30]	0.23 (0.03)***	0.24 [0.17, 0.30]
Use of digital technologies for personal purposes		0.05 (0.02)**	0.08 [0.01, 0.09]	0.05 (0.03)**	0.08 [0.01, 0.10]
School digital capacity degree		0.39 (0.08)***	0.26 [0.21, 0.56]		
Pedagogy: support and resources				0.38 (0.14)*	0.27 [0.08, 0.68]
Pedagogy: implementation in the classroom				-0.35 (0.12)*	-0.26 [-0.62, -0.07]
Assessment practices				0.38 (0.14)*	0.26 [0.08, 0.68]
Model fit					
AIC	1901.284	1742.499		1737.402	
BIC	1915.544	1775.773		1780.183	
logLLK	-947.6418	-864.2495		-859.7011	
R ² Marginal		0.20		0.23	
R ² Conditional	0.12	0.25		0.25	

Estimates and standard errors are from the multivariate random intercept model (dependent variable: students' DC).

*significant at the 0.05 level

**significant at the 0.01 level

***significant at the 0.001 level

Discussion

This study aimed to examine Basic VET students' DC perceptions and the personal and school factors influencing them. Two research questions were posed. To answer RQ1 (What are the attitudes toward ICTs, frequency of use of digital technologies and DC perceptions of Basic VET students in the BAC?), we conducted descriptive analyses of students' attitudes toward ICTs, their frequency use of digital technologies and their DC perceptions. For RQ2 (How do the school's degree of digital capacity, the SELFIE areas, and the students' personal characteristics influence Basic VET students' DC perceptions?), the impact of the school's digital capacity, the students' attitudes toward ICTs and their use of digital technologies for personal and school-related purposes were studied. Moreover, in order to determine which specific SELFIE areas and students' personal characteristics influence the students' DC perceptions, we made a breakdown of SELFIE areas to identify the strongest predictors.

Measures of the students' frequency of use of digital technologies indicated that these technologies are used more often for personal reasons than for school-related reasons. These results are consistent with those of previous studies (Aguilar de la Rosa, 2022; Burchert et al. 2013; Gisbert Cervera et al. 2016; Henríquez Coronel et al. 2018; Larraz 2013; Moreno Guerrero et al. 2019; Sánchez-Caballé et al. 2019) and make it clear that

students use digital technologies significantly more often for leisure purposes than for school-related tasks.

Regarding the students' DC perceptions, the highest results were obtained for multimedia literacy as in some previous studies (Llopis Nebot et al. 2018; Sánchez-Caballé et al. 2019). The lowest results were obtained in communication literacy, and it was concluded that students often do not respect Creative Commons licenses, with this aspect scoring the lowest, as in a previous study (Henríquez Coronel et al. 2018). The results on communication literacy indicate that while most students can easily use digital technologies for creating multimedia content or social communication, they struggle with more complex tasks like preparing a video curriculum vitae or creating a concept map. Therefore, it is concluded that being digitally competent requires other attitudes, skills and knowledge beyond the mere fact of knowing how to use digital technologies as a tool (Gallardo Echenique et al. 2015; Kennedy et al. 2009). Consequently, Basic VET students must strengthen their DC to meet the demands of a rapidly evolving digital landscape, where such competencies are not just educational goals but essential requirements for workforce integration and career resilience (Findeisen and Wild 2022).

In the modern economy, DC is not just an educational goal but a fundamental requirement for employability, enabling individuals to adapt to rapidly evolving work processes, interact with advanced digital systems, and solve complex problems in technology-rich environments (Van Laar et al., 2017). This necessitates fostering other attitudes, skills, and knowledge, such as critical thinking, digital collaboration, and ethical discernment.

The MLM analysis revealed that while the majority of differences in DC perceptions occurred between students within the same school, a meaningful portion of this variability was also attributable to systematic differences between schools themselves, suggesting that the school plays a role in determining those perceptions. It further revealed that students' DC perceptions are influenced by several personal and school factors. Regarding personal factors, the use of digital technologies was found to have a positive impact on students' DC, as concluded in previous analyses (Esteve Mon 2015; Findeisen and Wild 2022; González-Martínez et al. 2018; Zhong 2011). The use of digital technologies for both personal and school-related purposes encourages students to experiment and discover the opportunities offered by digital technologies as well as work on their digital skills.

Attitudes toward ICTs also showed a positive impact on students' DC in line with previous studies (Browne 2009; Edmunds et al. 2012; González-Martínez et al. 2018; Sang et al. 2010), indicating that students who have a positive attitude tend to develop their DC more. After all, when students have a favourable attitude toward ICTs, they are more open to exploring digital tools. Thus, they make a more effective and frequent use of technology, which in turn improves their DC. Hence, schools should create environments in which the active and meaningful use of digital technologies is encouraged since students are more likely to take advantage of opportunities to develop their DC when they believe that digital technologies are helpful to them and are motivated to use them.

At the school level, the degree of the school's digital capacity showed a positive impact on students' DC. Thus, when schools provide environments for students in which they can experiment and work with digital technologies, the students take advantage of the situation to work on their DC. The results of MLM showed that certain areas of school significantly impact students' DC more than others. One of those areas is the use of

digital technologies to support learning, which has a significant positive impact on students' DC. When teachers create and use digital technologies to support learning, they encourage more extensive and frequent interaction with those technologies, which is a key factor in fostering students' proficiency in digital environments and encouraging them to work on their DC. The use of digital technologies for assessment practices was also found to have a positive impact on students' DC: the use of digital technologies to assess and provide feedback to students is associated with better development of DC.

Surprisingly, the area regarding the implementation of digital technologies by innovating and adapting teaching and learning practices showed a significant negative impact on students' DC perception. This negative association could be due to several factors, one of which may be a lack of teacher training, as a failure to integrate technologies into the learning process in a meaningful way can have a negative impact. Moreover, if the use of these technologies is not aligned with the students' needs, this could also have a negative impact on the students' DC. As noted in a previous study (Findeisen and Wild 2022), if students do not perceive the activity as relevant, it will be difficult to work on DC. Given these results, and in line with other studies (Rauseo et al. 2022; Zhong 2011), we conclude that the mere use of digital technologies does not guarantee that students will work on their DC, and that the appropriate pedagogical use of these technologies is necessary in teaching and learning processes.

Finally, the results indicate that school factors are the strongest predictors of students' DC followed by attitude toward ICTs and the use of digital technologies for school-related and personal purposes. School predictors showed a significant impact on students' DC, however, interestingly, variability among schools was low. These results are in line with the assumption that students do not possess sufficient digital skills (Kirschner and De Bruyckere 2017) and, therefore, need appropriate academic environments and guidance to work on their DC. Hence, it is essential for schools to provide an environment in which students may attain proficiency in their DC in an educational setting (European Commission 2020). It is also worth noting that personal factors are important for students' DC and that schools should focus on fostering their development by designing learning experiences that build self-efficacy and positive attitudes towards technology, thereby maximising students' digital potential."

Limitations and further research

This study has certain limitations. First, similar results were obtained across different schools, yielding low variability. Although the predictors are statistically significant, this low variability could indicate that some predictors may be missing. Second, the assessment of students' DC relied on self-reported data, which may not fully align with objectively measured levels. Consequently, interpretations of the findings should acknowledge that results reflect subjective perceptions rather than demonstrated abilities. Moreover, as the study was conducted based solely on quantitative data, additional interpretations and a deeper understanding of the results were not possible. Further qualitative research could be helpful to achieve a richer and deeper analysis of the full situation.

Further research should include teacher-level data in the MLM to explore how teachers' Digital Competence (TDC) and their use of digitalisation in teaching influence students' DC, providing deeper insights into how teachers' practices influence students' DC. Additionally, as INCOTIC 2.0 offers a holistic approach to DC, it would be useful

to do more research on other educational stages, as well as in the rest of VET levels with this instrument. Finally, we investigated students' perceived DC primarily with reference to school, although we also aimed to demonstrate the relevance of the use of technology in everyday working life. In cases in which the vocational system involves alternance between school and the workplace, it would be interesting to further investigate how the work-related component of students' DC relates to the school- and leisure time-related components.

Conclusions

This study aimed to provide a picture of the DC perceptions of today's Basic VET students in the BAC in order to identify factors that have an impact on these students' DC and to identify the strongest predictors of their DC.

It is important to highlight the originality of the present work in the context of the BAC, as it provides a snapshot of this specific context of VET and digitalisation. Moreover, the results of the present study revealed that students need to work on their DC, guided by their teachers and school policies. Although these students are competent in their use of digital tools in their leisure activities, being fully digitally competent involves attitudes, skills, and knowledge that go beyond mere instrumental and personal usage. Furthermore, it was demonstrated that school digital implementation is one of the strongest factors of students' DC, followed by personal factors.

These results make a significant contribution to the field of DC and digitalisation in education, offering policymakers not only a comprehensive understanding of Basic VET students' DC specifically, but also knowledge of the factors that must be considered when promoting educational opportunities to work on students' DC in general. On a more practical level, it provides an opportunity for school management and teachers to reflect on the need to develop DC with students, as the present results suggest that Basic VET students do not possess the appropriate digital skills often attributed to them. Given the importance of DC in today's world, all students must acquire appropriate digital skills in order to participate fully in society and be adequately prepared for the labour market. It is therefore essential to work on DC with Basic VET students. The results and reflections of the present study provide an opportunity to identify further areas for improvement and to implement innovations in helping students to develop their DC.

Abbreviations

VET	Vocational education training
DC	Digital competence
BAC	Basque Autonomous Community

Supplementary Information

The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40461-025-00198-0>.

Supplementary Material 1

Author contributions

A.ZP was responsible for conceptualisation, data curation, methodology, analysis, visualisation and writing. A.C, A.I.A, and V.I.M contributed through supervision and writing – review & editing. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Data availability

No datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

Declarations**Human ethics and consent to participate**

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the American Psychological Association. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were all over the age of 16. No further ethical approval was required according to institutional and national guidelines.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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References

- Basque Government (2015), September 15 *Formación profesional: Formación Profesional Básica*. <https://www.euskadi.eus/informacion/formacion-profesional-basica/web01-a2hlanhz/es/>
- Basque Government (2016), November 3 *Formación profesional: Estructura organizativa*. <https://www.euskadi.eus/informacion/formacion-profesional/web01-a2hlanhz/es/>
- Basque Government (2022a) *6º Plan vasco de formación profesional* (1ª ed). Eusko Jaurilaritzaren Argitalpen Zerbitzu Nagusia = Servicio Central de Publicaciones del Gobierno Vasco
- Basque Government (2022b) *Plan de transformación digital del sistema educativo vasco*
- Browne J (2009) Assessing pre-service teacher attitudes and skills with the technology integration confidence scale. *Comput Sch* 26(1):4–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07380560802688240>
- Burchert J, Katterfeldt E-S, Sven S, Zeising A (2013) Azubis online.: Über die kompetenzen und motive der nutzung des internets in der ausbildung. *MERZ Z Für Medienpädagogik* 57:97–107
- Cattaneo A, Antonietti C, Rauseo M (2022) How digitalised are vocational teachers? Assessing digital competence in vocational education and looking at its underlying factors. *Comput Educ* 176:104358. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2021.104358>
- Cedefop (2023a) Going digital means skilling for digital: using big data to track emerging digital skill needs. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/> <https://doi.org/10.2801/772175>
- Cedefop (2023b), October 5 *Vocational education and training in Spain*. CEDEFOP. <https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/publications/4214>
- Costa P, Castaño-Muñoz J, Kampylis P (2021) Capturing schools' digital capacity: psychometric analyses of the SELFIE self-reflection tool. *Comput Educ* 162:104080. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2020.104080>
- Aguilar de la Rosa, A. (2022). La competencia digital de los estudiantes de Formación Profesional: Una revisión sistemática. *Revista Interuniversitaria de Investigación En Tecnología Educativa*, 13, 200–221. <https://doi.org/10.6018/riite.545311>
- Edmunds R, Thorpe M, Conole G (2012) Student attitudes towards and use of ICT in course study, work and social activity: a technology acceptance model approach. *Br J Educ Technol* 43(1):71–84. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8535.2010.01142.x>
- Espuny Vidal C, González Martínez J, Lleixà Fortuño M, Gisbert Cervera M (2011) University students' attitudes towards and expectations of the educational use of social networks. *RUSC Univ Knowl Soc J* 8(1):171–185. <https://doi.org/10.7238/rusc.v8i1.839>
- Estanyol E, Montaña M, Fernández-de-Castro P, Aranda D, Mohammadi L (2023) Digital competence among young people in Spain: a gender divide analysis. *Comunicar* 31(74):113–123. <https://doi.org/10.3916/C74-2023-09>
- Esteve Mon FM (2015) La competencia digital docente: análisis de La autopercepción y evaluación Del Desempeño de Los estudiantes Universitarios de educación Por medio de Un Entorno 3D. *Universitas Tarraconensis Revista De Ciències De l'Educació* 1(1):88. <https://doi.org/10.17345/ute.2015.1.662>
- European Commission (2020) *Digital Education Action Plan* (COM(2020) 624 Final)
- European Commission (2022b), December 5 *SELFIE | European Education Area*. SELFIE. <https://education.ec.europa.eu/selfie>
- European Education and Culture Executive Agency (2019) *Structural indicators for monitoring education and training systems in Europe 2019: Overview of major reforms since 2015*. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/> <https://doi.org/10.2797/256641>
- European Commission (2019) Key competences for lifelong learning. Publications Office, Luxembourg. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2766/569540>
- European Commission (2022a) Measuring digital skills across the EU: digital skills indicator 2.0. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/897803>
- Findeisen S, Wild S (2022) General digital competences of beginning trainees in commercial vocational education and training. *Empir Res Vocat Educ Train* 14(2). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40461-022-00130-w>
- Fraillon J, Ainley J, Schulz W, Friedman T, Gebhardt E (2014) Preparing for life in a digital age: the IEA international computer and information literacy study international report. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-1422-2-7>
- Fuster-Rico A, Aparicio-Flores MdelP, Pérez-Marco M, Ros NA (2025) Diferencias En El Nivel de competencia digital de Los adolescentes Españoles En Función Del género, Las Faltas de asistencia escolar y La evaluación académica. *Eur Public Social Innov Rev* 10:1–14. <https://doi.org/10.31637/epsir-2025-301>
- Gallardo Echenique EE, Marqués Molías L, Bullen M (2015) Students in higher education: social and academic uses of digital technology. *RUSC Univ Knowl Soc J* 12(1):25. <https://doi.org/10.7238/rusc.v12i1.2078>

- Gisbert Cervera M, González Martínez J, Esteve Mon FM (2016) Competencia digital y competencia digital docente: Una panorámica sobre El Estado de La cuestión. *Revista Interuniversitaria De Investigación En Tecnología Educativa* 74–83. <https://doi.org/10.6018/riite2016/257631>
- González-Martínez J, M Esteve-Mon F, Larraz Rada V, Espuny Vidal C, Gisbert Cervera M (2018) INCOTIC 2.0. Una Nueva Herramienta Para La autoevaluación de La competencia digital Del alumnado universitario. *Profesorado Revista De Currículum Y Formación Del Profesorado* 22(4):133–152. <https://doi.org/10.30827/profesorado.v22i4.8401>
- Hatlevik OE, Guðmundsdóttir GB, Loi M (2015) Examining factors predicting students' digital competence. *J Inf Technol Educ Res* 14:123–137. <https://doi.org/10.28945/2126>
- Henríquez Coronel P, Fernández F, I., Trámpuz JP (2018) La evaluación de la competencia digital auto percibida de los universitarios ULEAM. In X. Carrera, F. Martínez Sánchez, J. L. Coiduras Rodríguez, E. Brescó Baiges, & E. Vaquero Tió (Eds.), *EDUcación con TECnología: Un compromiso social. Aproximaciones desde la investigación y la innovación*. Edicions de la Universitat de Lleida. <https://doi.org/10.21001/edutec.2018>
- Hippe R, Jakubowski M (eds) (2022) Is student digital competence shaped by schools or individual factors? Insights from SELFIE using multilevel models. Publications Office of the European Union
- Indrawan PA, Lay AE (2019) Guidance and counseling teachers' competency perspective in the era of industrial revolution 4.0. *Int J Innov Creativity Change* 5(3):147–161
- Kennedy G, Dalgarno B, Bennett S, Gray K, Waycott J, Judd T, Bishop A, Maton K, Krause K-L, Chang R (2009) Educating the net generation: A handbook of findings for practice and policy. Australian Learning and Teaching Council
- Kirschner PA, De Bruyckere P (2017) The myths of the digital native and the multitasker. *Teach Teach Educ* 67:135–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2017.06.001>
- Kivunja C (2015) Teaching students to learn and to work well with 21st century skills: unpacking the career and life skills domain of the new learning paradigm. *Int J High Educ* 4(1):p1. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v4n1p1>
- Kovalchuk VI, Maslich SV, Movchan LH (2023) Digitalization of vocational education under crisis conditions. *Educational Technol Q* 2023(1):1–17. <https://doi.org/10.55056/etq.49>
- Larraz V La competencia digital a la Universitat [Ph.D., Thesis (2013) Universitat d'Andorra]. In *TDX (Tesis Doctorals en Xarxa)*. <https://www.tdx.cat/handle/10803/113431>
- Llopis Nebot MÁ, Segura A, Francesc Marc J, Aparicio EMP, J., Valdeolivas Novella G (2018) Competencia digital y pensamiento computacional en el grado de maestro en educación primaria. In X. Carrera, F. Martínez Sánchez, J. L. Coiduras Rodríguez, E. Brescó Baiges, & E. Vaquero Tió (Eds.), *EDUcación con TECnología: Un compromiso social. Aproximaciones desde la investigación y la innovación*. Edicions de la Universitat de Lleida. <https://doi.org/10.21001/edutec.2018>
- Lucas M, Bem-Haja P, Siddiq F, Moreira A, Redecker C (2021) The relation between in-service teachers' digital competence and personal and contextual factors: what matters most? *Comput Educ* 160:104052. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2020.104052>
- Moreno Guerrero AJ, Cabrera F, A., López Belmonte J (2019) Las competencias digitales Del alumnado de Formación profesional básica. *Revista De Educación De La Universidad De Granada* 26:9–33. <https://doi.org/10.30827/reugra.v26i0.111>
- Niño-Cortés LM, Grimalt-Álvaro C, Lores-Gómez B, Usart M (2023) Brecha digital de Género En secundaria: diferencias En competencia autopercebida y actitud Hacia La tecnología. *Educación XX1* 26(2):299–322. <https://doi.org/10.5944/educxx1.34587>
- PrenDES M-P, Castañeda L, Gutiérrez I (2010) ICT competences of future teachers. *Comunicar* 18(35):175–182. <https://doi.org/10.3916/C35-2010-03-11>
- Rauseo M, Harder A, Glassey-Previdoli D, Cattaneo A, Schumann S, Imboden S (2022) Same, but different?? Digital transformation in Swiss vocational schools from the perspectives of school management and teachers. *Technol Knowl Learn* 28:407–427. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10758-022-09631-9>
- Sánchez-Caballé A, Gisbert-Cervera M, Esteve-Mon F (2019) La competencia digital de Los estudiantes universitarios de primer Curso de Grado. *Innoeduca Int J Technol Educational Innov* 5(2):104–113. <https://doi.org/10.24310/innoeduca.2019.v5i2.5598>
- Sang G, Valcke M, van Braak J, Tondeur J (2010) Student teachers' thinking processes and ICT integration: predictors of prospective teaching behaviors with educational technology. *Comput Educ* 54(1):103–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2009.07.010>
- Schmitz M-L, Antonietti C, Cattaneo A, Gonon P, Petko D (2022) When barriers are not an issue: tracing the relationship between hindering factors and technology use in secondary schools across Europe. *Comput Educ* 179:104411. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2021.104411>
- Spanish Government (2020) *Plan de Modernización de la Formación Profesional*
- Subrahmanyam Gita (2022). Digital skills development in TVET teacher training: UNESCO-UNEVOC trends mapping study. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED619368>
- Valverde-Crespo D, de Pro-Bueno A, González-Sánchez J (2020) La Información científica En internet Vista Por estudiantes de educación secundaria obligatoria: Un estudio exploratorio de Sus competencias digitales. *Revista Eureka Sobre Enseñanza Y Divulgación De Las Ciencias* 17(1):110101–110118
- Van Laar E, van Deursen A, JAM, van Dijk JAGM, de Haan J (2017) The relation between 21st-century skills and digital skills: A systematic literature review. *Computers in Human Behavior* 72:577–588. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2017.03.010>
- Verdú-Pina M, Grimalt-Álvaro C, Usart M, Gisbert-Cervera M (2024) La competencia digital de estudiantes y Docentes En Los Centros de educación secundaria. *EduTec Revista Electrónica De Tecnología Educativa* 87:87. <https://doi.org/10.21556/edutec.2024.87.3061>
- Wild S, Schulze Heuling L (2020) How do the digital competences of students in vocational schools differ from those of students in cooperative higher education institutions in germany?? *Empir Res Vocat Educ Train* 12(5). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40461-020-00091-y>
- Zhao Y, Llorente P, A. M., Sánchez Gómez MC (2021) Digital competence in higher education research: A systematic literature review. *Comput Educ* 168:104–212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2021.104212>
- Zhong Z-J (2011) From access to usage: the divide of self-reported digital skills among adolescents. *Comput Educ* 56(3):736–746. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2010.10.016>

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